

THE DEVELOPMENT OF FEMINISM IN MODERN ENGLISH LITERATURE

Davletova Shalola

Teacher at Uzbekistan State World Languages

University, Tashkent city, Uzbekistan

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Abstract. In the history of English Literature 19th century is the greatest period having many female writers and works dedicated to the rights of women. This timespan transformed the social and cultural traditions of modern Britain with its new insight and unique perspective, combined with rational and critical thinking, and many writers expressed their understanding and praise of women's wisdom and personality charm. Among them Bronte sisters, case in point, created a lot of strong personalities in their works, advanced consciousness of the female image, produced a strong voice of female. Others from contemporary literature of Britain: Mary Wollstonecraft, Virginia Woolf, Mary Ellman, Fay Weldon and many others aimed to have the same opportunity for education, occupation and life as men. The perception of an independent woman has changed throughout the centuries as well, from a woman who was supposed to be a wife, mother, and keeper of a household, more precisely how Martin Luther claimed: "Women should remain at home, sit still, keep house, and bear and bring up children. A woman is, or at least should be, a friendly, courteous, and a merry companion in life, the honour and ornament of the house, and inclined to tenderness, for there unto are they chiefly created, to bear children, and to be the pleasure, joy and solace of their husbands," to a woman who does not even need a man to find her happiness and her occupation can be whatever she wants. The aim of this article to give brief information about the women who carried out these perspectives actively.

Keywords: Feminism · English literature · thought · consciousness awakening

Development of British Feminism

Earlier, feminism was limited to some female writers only but the increased number of female writers and the representation of women characters in fiction world drew large attention in the literature. First Wave Feminism mainly concerned with the treatment of women in the male-dominated society. The major works which raised the issues of feminism during this phase are Mary Ellman's *Thinking about Women* (1968), Kate Millet's *Sexual Politics* (1969) and Germaine Greer's *The Female Eunuch* (1970). Many important works of the male writers have been studied in order to analyze the attitude of male towards women and society. Second Wave Feminism is concerned with women writings

include Ellen More's *Literary Women* (1976), Elaine Showalter's *A Literature of Their Own* (1970), Nina Baym's *Women's Fiction* (1978) , Sandra Gilbert and Susan Gubar's *The Mad Woman in the Attic* (1979), and Margaret Homan's *Women Writers and Poetic Identity* (1980). Elaine Showalter's *A Literature of Their Own* published in 1970, proposes three stages in the history of feminist writings: Feminine phase (1840-80), in which women writers imitated dominant male artistic norms and aesthetic standards; Feminist phase (1880-1920), in which radical approach has been maintained; and at last Female phase (1920-onwards) which primarily focused on female writing and female experiences.

Mary Wollstonecraft

She was one of the authors who wrote about feminism, advocates in her *A Vindication of the Rights of Women* (1792) that **women must be treated equally because they have to play a crucial and vital role in society especially bringing up children.** She attacks male thinker and scholar like Rousseau who argued that women did not need an education but she supported education as means of women's improvement.

Margaret Fuller

Like other feminist activist, she was one of the famous female writers of the 19th century, in her *Women in the Nineteenth Century* (1845) believed that **education is the means of emancipation for women and her keys planks are education, employment and political.**

Virginia Woolf

While in the twentieth century a **modernist and female Victorian author, Virginia Woolf explored gender relations** in her *A Room of One's Own* (1929) and *Three Guineas* (1938). She vehemently argued that the patriarchal education systems and reading practices prevent women readers from reading as women. It is also remarkable when she remarks '**a woman must have money and a room of her own if she to write fiction**'. She advocates for the liberation of women, financially independence and right to reveal feelings and experiences through words.

Simone De Beauvoir

She favours that there is '**no essence**' of the woman and a woman is constructed by men. As she states it in her feminism manifesto *The Second Sex* (1949): '**One is not born a woman but become one**'. The exploitation, discrimination and the crisis of women's identification faced by women in the society have questioned by female writers, activists, and critics. In relation to literature,

feminism movement has focused on the role played by literature to bring out gender discrimination, domestic violence, and inequality on the forefront.

Prominent British Feminist writers and their works

Charlotte Bronte

Charlotte Bronte's *Jane Eyre* was published under her pen name Currer Bell in 1847, which was a period when women were still oppressed, had no rights nor were respected among men. The publication caused both high acclaim and harsh criticism because of how the author dealt with the topic of sexuality. In the infamous Elizabeth Rigby's review of *Jane Eyre* is even suggested that if the book was written by a woman "she would forfeited the society of her own sex." (30) The puritan Victorian readership criticized the author's sex, suggesting that such behaviour is not appropriate for a woman, female character of even a female writer. The harsh critiques advocated that Jane's description as a strong, self-sufficient woman with no obligations to men is a quality only belonging to men, thus is unnatural for women. Jane's passionate rebellion was perceived by some as absolutely unacceptable suggesting that women are supposed to be subordinate to men. Bulwer Lytton in her letter on *Jane Eyre* even complains that "British females are intense men worshippers – and in their disgusting books the young ladies make all the advances – and do all the love-making – and this flatters the hoggish vanity of English men." (31) In spite of the criticism the novel was still a success. Bronte developed a type of heroine who was fearless, firm, independent and did not need to depend on a man, yet who calls for true love and for equality. Bronte created a character that is unlike any other, Jane Eyre seeks dignity and respect, and throughout the book the reader see the evolution of the protagonist. Jane describes herself as: "I am 19 no bird; and no net ensnares me: I am a free human being with an independent will." (32) Even though Jane was always strong, her maturation throughout the novel gives her the ability to cope with unfortunate events in her life more readily. When she found out that the man she loved was already married, she was able to control herself, and even though leaving Mr. Rochester made her feel miserable, betrayed, and her sorrow was overwhelming, she was still able to break free.³³ Jane did not perceived her life to be fulfilled only if she got married, that is also reason why she left Mr. Rochester, and despite loving him she was strong and independent enough to continue working as a governess and teacher although this occupation was no better than being a servant.

Thomas Hardy

The second part of the 19th century was the era when women started to realize that being a wife and mother without having the opportunity to study or to have a proper job is not acceptable. The term feminism was not coined yet, nor there were any female groups supporting women's rights, however, Hardy portrayed some of his female characters as feminists. In *Far From the Madding Crowd* (1874), the protagonist, Bathsheba Everdene, is portrayed as a feisty feminist, who as she says: "Well, what I mean is that I shouldn't mind being a bride at a wedding, if I could be one without having a husband." (44) It was not only the protagonist in *Far From the Madding Crowd* who is a feminist, but also other characters in Hardy's novels, such as Tess in *Tess of the d'Urbervilles* or Sue in *Jude the Obscure* can be perceived as feminists. However, as states Alisar M. Duckworth in her essay *Women and Sexuality in the Novels of Thomas Hardy*, Hardy was seemed misogynist predominantly to Victorian readers. Mainly because he "neglected to provide comforting portraits of women finding the proper outlet for their energy in marriage," (45). Moreover, rebellious Hardy disputed the idea that marriage is the only goal of a woman's sexuality. The author also criticized the 23 Victorian patriarchy by the critique of the legal system, he did not agree with the fact that a woman should hand over all her property to her husband after getting married, which Hardy also illustrated very well in the following quote: "It appears that ordinary men take wives because possession is not possible without marriage, and that ordinary women accept husbands because marriage is not possible without possession; with totally differing aims the method is the same on both sides. But the understood incentive on the woman's part was wanting here. Besides, Bathsheba's position as absolute mistress of a farm and house was a novel one, and the novelty had not yet begun to wear off." (47) Hardy's *Far From the Madding Crowd* promotes a feminist ideology that suggest that women are as strong and capable of having power in work and romantic relationship as men are,⁴⁸ which shows Hardy's approval of female autonomy.

Conclusion

The aim of this paper was to explore the development of feminism in British literature. I focused on the history of the phenomenon and also dwells on views of the different writers each from a different time period. Feminism questions the long-standing, dominant, male interpretations, phallogocentric ideology and patriarchal attitude. It concerned with varied aspects of feminism. As Showalter sums up, "English feminist criticism, essentially Marxist, stressed oppression, French feminist criticism, especially psychoanalyst, stresses oppression."

However, all have become 'gynocentric'. Feminism criticism also concerned with women's language and they need to cultivate linguistic and stylistic devices that can spontaneously express feminine sensibility and individuality.

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